

ML-based Resolution Time Prediction of Trouble Ticket for Operational Telecommunication Networks

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Introduction: Thousands of interconnected network equipment are run by Internet Service Providers (ISP). ISPs make use of these pieces of equipment to provide stable network connectivity to customers. When malfunctioning is detected in any of these components, an alarm is generated depending on the type of the error. A large number of alarms that are flooding the network operation centers of telecommunication companies generate Trouble Tickets (TT). TTs are e-records that carry information about outages and document actions taken throughout their lifetime [1]. Predicting the Resolution Time (RT) of these TTs is of importance since it has a great impact on how to optimize the network operations, minimize network downtime, and hence maximize customer satisfaction.

Some previous work exists on the issue of RT prediction of TTs in networks, and in general in large systems. Some works [2]–[4] focus on classifying the tickets according to their root causes. Sample et al. [1] in Predicting Trouble Ticket Resolution focus on RT by applying both classification and regression models to predict the RT of the tickets. They trained their models on around 12000 TTs and the MAE of 24.8 hours was achieved with the best regression model.

Telenor is continuously striving to optimize network performance and offer the best possible customer experience to its customers. To that end, Telenor participates in the EU-funded SEMANTIC research collaboration to leverage network and service data that are continuously generated in all Telenor operational networks to optimize through machine learning, network performance, and customer experience. This research work is part of the above effort. Our work aims at predicting the RT of Telenor’s network TTs. In Telenor’s systems, some features are added to the TTs at the time of their creation and some other features are added later in the lifetime of the tickets. In this work, we mainly focus on the features available at the time of ticket creation and investigate the correlation between these features and the resolution time of the tickets [5]. Such features are used to build machine learning (ML) models and predict the RT directly *at the time of ticket creation*. Our ultimate goal is to build these ML models based on available historical tickets and use them to predict the time resolution for future tickets. In doing so, we intend to pave the way to correlate the network tickets’ RT with the different type of issues and their most probable root causes (software issues, electricity breakdowns, fiber cuts, hardware issues, human errors, security breaches, etc.). This in turn can

ultimately lead to improved and automated network healing when handling issues for each type of root cause category. As a result, for some of the root causes, indeed, the success in a better prediction of the TT resolution time will also imply a better Quality of Experience (QoE) for the end-users [5].

Brief System Description: Trouble tickets are generated by fault management systems when equipment in the network does not respond to certain monitoring events within a predefined time span. In such a case, the fault management system generates an alarm that is automatically converted into a TT. TTs can also be generated manually by technicians that supervise the network’s operation [6]. Alarm tracking is handled by a separate internal system. The alarms could be generated by malfunctioning of network equipment, degradation of a signal, a power outage, fiber cuts, etc. [6]. After ticket creation, the information related to the ticket (such as the name of the affected node, the number of potentially affected customers, and the probable root cause of the ticket generation) is filled automatically by the system [6]. Some tickets are resolved automatically after their creation. If they are not resolved automatically, a group of technicians is assigned to troubleshoot the problem. If the technicians fail to remotely resolve the problem, an in-place technician is dispatched to the site where the problem happened. In-site problems are usually of two categories: power failures and fiber breaks. In case of power failures, the problem normally takes a few hours to be resolved. However, in case of fiber breaks, the repair can take longer. After resolving the problem, information about the error and actions taken are added to the ticket, and the ticket status is marked as solved in the system. This is how a TT evolves through its life cycle [5]–[7].

Data Preperation: The data used in this study comes from a trouble ticket handling system that Telenor uses to store and review TTs. This data contains 39,020 tickets, aggregated over the years. Each ticket has 17 features that were added to the ticket at the creation time. Most features are categorical and some of them are numerical. They include information such as the time and date of ticket creation and ticket resolution, geographical data, the type and technology of affected equipment, postcode, and location of the affected site. Categorical features were one-hot encoded in such a way that two values 0 and 1 were considered for each category, if the ticket contains that category, we mark it as 1, otherwise, we mark it as 0. Numerical features were also scaled to have a distribution of

Fig. 1: Distribution of the samples' RT (Frequency vs. resolution time in minutes).

0 mean and 1 standard deviation. Some of the features are in free text so they need to be explored. After extracting the important information from these free text features, they were removed. We also removed some features such as date features, model, and hostname of the equipment since they are of little importance for training the ML models. In the end, we were left with 21 features for each ticket. The tickets were also pre-processed and cleaned, addressing for instance missing values. Also, we imputed the missing values of categorical columns with constant values and missing values of numerical columns with the Bayesian Ridge imputation technique [7], [8].

The distribution plot of the TT resolution time samples is shown in Figure 1. Note that the last bin is the aggregation of all samples with RT of more than 1000 minutes. We consider the samples sitting in 2% upper quantile of time resolution distribution as outliers and removed them. Furthermore, we divided the data set into 3 subsets: The training set which is used for training the models, the validation set which is used for hyperparameter tuning of the models, and the test set which is used for testing the performance of the models. Several ML-based regression models were leveraged to address the prediction problem. Regression techniques were chosen for this specific problem since the target variable (RT in minutes) is continuous. 5 different regression models were considered concretely: Linear Regression (LR) [9], Decision Tree (DT) [10], Random Forests (RF) [11], Adaptive boosting (ADA) [12], [13] and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB) [14]. 3-fold cross-validation and Bayesian optimization [15] method were conducted for all methods to tune the hyperparameters and optimize the results on Mean Absolute Error (MAE) metrics.

Numerical Evaluation & Discussion: The regression models were trained on the training set and optimized on the validation set. Table I shows the MAE results on test set.

As shown in Table I, the XGB obtained the lowest MAE among other models on the test set. We furthermore split the train and test set into three subsets, each containing an equal number of samples, to evaluate XGB performance on specific subsets representing different ticket RT ranges. We consider subset 1 as tickets that are resolved in a short period of time, subset 2 as tickets that are resolved in a medium period of time, and subset 3 as tickets that are resolved in a long period of time. We consider 2 settings to do this experiment. For each

TABLE I: MAE Results (in minutes)

Regressor	Train MAE	Val MAE	Test MAE
LR	257.04	259.14	256.94
DT	87.60	111.50	108.87
RF	51.86	92.69	87.12
ADA	173.83	172.28	173.59
XGB	35.77	80.08	79.29

TABLE II: XGB MAE Results for 2 Settings (in minutes)

Subset	RT Range	MAE (setting1)	MAE (setting2)
Subset1	[0,40)	57.92	5.37
Subset2	[40,135)	47.51	18.43
Subset3	[135, ∞)	131.98	139.32

setting, we tune the hyperparameters of XGB with respect to its validation set. In the first setting, we train the XGB model on all training samples and evaluate it on each individual test subset. In the second setting, we train the model separately on each individual train subset and evaluate the performance of each model on the corresponding test subset. The results achieved by both settings are shown in Table II. Based on these results, we come to the conclusion that our XGB model has the best performance in predicting the time resolution of tickets. Moreover, results on the two settings show us that prior knowledge of ticket classes (short, medium, and long resolution time) significantly improves the performance of the model. We will address this issue in our future works, where a classifier will be trained to first classify the tickets according to these 3 classes and then the best regression model will be engaged to predict the RT of the tickets.

Acknowledgment: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 861165.

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